

D2.1 Plan for the community co-creation activities

Authors: Claudia Fabó Cartas (ECSA) and Jorge Barba (IBERCIVIS)

*Contributors: Carla Perucca Iannitelli (SfC),
Alejandro Gonzalo (IBERCIVIS) and Simona
Cerrato (ECSA)*

28.02.2023

Disclaimer

The information, documentation and figures in this deliverable are written by the European Citizen Science (ECS) project Consortium under EC grant agreement No. 101058509 and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

All European Citizen Science (ECS) Consortium members are committed to publish accurate and up to date information and take the greatest care to do so. However, the consortium members cannot accept liability for any direct, indirect, special, consequential or other losses or damages of any kind arising out of the use of this information.

Acknowledgment

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Reference

Please cite this work as:

Fabó Cartas, C., Barba, J., Perucca Iannitelli, C., Gonzalo, A., Cerrato, S. (2023) D2.1 Plan for the community co-creation activities. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10615167>

Copyright Notice

This work by Parties of the European Citizen Science (ECS) Consortium is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence.

Document Identification Sheet

Project Ref. No.	101058509
Project acronym	ECS
Project Full Name	European Citizen Science
Document Name	ECS_D2.1_Plan for the community co-creation activities_20230228.pdf
Security	PU
Contractual Date of Delivery	Month 5, 31.12.2022; postponed to Month 7, 28.02.2023
Actual Date of Delivery	28 February 2023; resubmission with small changes on 07.07.2023
Type	R – Document, report
Deliverable number	D2.1
Deliverable name	Plan for the community co-creation activities
WP / Lead Beneficiary	WP2 / ECSA
Number of pages	56
Authors	Claudia Fabó Cartas (ECSA) and Jorge Barba (IBERCIVIS)
Contributors	Carla Perucca Iannitelli (SfC), Alejandro Gonzalo (IBERCIVIS), and Simona Cerrato (ECSA)
Review	Alex Amo (SfC), Muki Haklay (UP), Cléa Montanari (UP), Barbara Kieslinger (ZSI)
Project Officer	Irina Elena Tiron
Abstract	This deliverable provides a plan for the community engagement activities as part of T2.1 and for the co-design of new platform services and features as part of T2.2 and T2.3. The document contains a section on how inclusivity will be considered in these.
Keywords	ECS, citizen science, community engagement, co-design, stakeholder engagement, events, community building

Table of contents

List of figures.....	5
List of tables	5
List of definitions and acronyms.....	6
Network of the Heads of European Environmental Protection Agencies	6
Executive Summary	7
Introduction.....	8
Project Background.....	9
Project description.....	9
1. Community engagement in ECS.....	14
1.1. The importance of engaging the community in the project.....	14
1.2. Stakeholder engagement.....	16
1.3. Community engagement events.....	18
1.3.1. Steps to plan the community engagement events.....	18
1.3.2. Types of community engagement events	20
1.3.3. Evaluation of community engagement events.....	24
1.3.4. ECS community engagement events: guidelines for planning and communicating	25
2. Co-design methodology in ECS	28
2.1. Introduction to co-design methodologies.....	28
2.2. Learning from Cos4Cloud: key concepts	29
2.3. A yearly cycle in the ECS co-design process.....	31
2.3.1. Phase 1 - Communication strategy.....	31
2.3.2. Phase 2 - Definition of the cycle: activities and timetable	32
2.3.3. Phase 3 - Activities for participatory selection.....	33
2.3.4. Phase 4 - Development of selected services	34
2.3.5. Phase 5 - Co-design and testing.....	34
2.3.6. Phase 6 - Co-evaluation	35
2.4. Timetable approach for an annual cycle in the ECS co-design process	35
3. Inclusivity.....	38
3.1. ECS approach towards inclusiveness.....	38
3.2. What will we do?	38
4. Evaluation and co-evaluation of community engagement and co-design activities.....	40
5. Concluding remarks and next steps.....	42
References	43
Annex A – Description of additional activities for the ECS co-design process.....	45
Annex B – Activities extracted from Guasch et al. (2022).....	47

Version Log

Version	Date	Released by	Nature of Change
0.1	29.11.2022 – 07.12.2022	Claudia Fabó Cartas (ECSA) and Jorge Barba (IBERCIVIS)	First structure of the deliverable and outline
0.2	17.01.2023	Claudia Fabó Cartas (ECSA), Jorge Barba (IBERCIVIS)	First draft
0.3	22.02.2023	Claudia Fabó Cartas (ECSA), Jorge Barba (IBERCIVIS), Simona Cerrato (ECSA), Carla Perucca Iannitelli (SfC)	Version ready for peer-review
0.4	22.02.2023 – 24.02.2023	Alex Amo (SfC), Muki Haklay (UP), Cléa Montanari (UP), Barbara Kieslinger (ZSI)	Peer-review
0.5	27.02.2023	Claudia Fabó Cartas (ECSA), Jorge Barba (IBERCIVIS) and Carla Perucca Iannitelli (SfC)	Final edits based on reviewers' feedback
1.0	28.02.2023	Claudia Fabó Cartas (ECSA)	Final version ready for submission
2.0	06.07.2023	Claudia Fabó Cartas (ECSA)	Update of the document to comply with ECS visual identity and adapted EU funding acknowledgement

List of figures

Figure 1. ECS work package structure.....	13
Figure 2. Cos4Cloud approach to co-design (Cos4Cloud consortium 2023).....	29
Figure 3. Gantt chart of a yearly cycle in the ECS co-design process.....	31
Figure 4. DITOs escalator framework for public engagement (Skarlatidou & Haklay 2021).	39

List of tables

Table 1. Participants in the ECS Consortium – 12 beneficiaries and 9 Affiliated Entities.	11
Table 2. Examples of various types of engagement events.....	21
Table 3. Events organised by ECS partners to link or couple ECS community engagement events.	22
Table 4. Completed or planned engagement events (at least 25 over the course of the project).....	23
Table 5. Dedicated communication activities directly supporting community building.	24
Table 6. Communication worksheet.....	27
Table 7. Table of activities that can be carried out in a cycle.	33
Table 8. Timetable approach for an annual cycle in the ECS co-design process.....	36

List of definitions and acronyms

Acronym	Expansion
CS	Citizen science
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
Data	Information, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images. The focus is on research data that is available in digital form (European Commission 2016).
DG	Directorate-General of the European Commission
EC	European Commission
ECS	European Citizen Science
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPA Network	Network of the Heads of European Environmental Protection Agencies
ERA	European Research Area
EU R&I Days	EU Research and Innovation Days
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FP7	7th Framework Programme for Research
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
RTOs	Research and Technology Organisations
T	Task
UN	United Nations
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The 'Plan for the community co-creation activities' is Deliverable 2.1 (D2.1) from the EU-funded project European Citizen Science. This deliverable is part of WP2 'Strengthening links and collaboration', which has the overall objective to strengthen and expand the citizen science community. The WP aims to gather existing and new actors in citizen science in the journey of co-creation.

The current deliverable focuses on the activities of tasks 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3: on building the European citizen science community of the future, selecting the new services for the eu-citizen.science platform in a participatory way, and co-designing and developing new services for the platform. The tasks are related as explained in the introduction section.

The core of T2.1 will be a series of engagement activities throughout the project named "community engagement events" (at least 25 at European and national level) and workshops with the ECSA working groups. T2.2 is on the participatory selection of new services for the eu-citizen.science platform. Its objective is to identify and prioritise the development of at least five new services to be offered to the citizen science community and integrated into the platform. T2.3 concentrates on the co-design and development of said new services for the platform and is therefore closely interlinked to T2.2.

The objective of this document is to present a plan for 1) the community engagement events and 2) the co-design of services for the eu-citizen.science platform that informs and provides the rationale for the activities in T2.1, T2.2 and T2.3 mentioned and serves as a guide and reference document to plan

said activities. As the first rounds of community engagement events and co-design activities are carried out over the next months, the plan will be adapted and further refined as needed.

The first part of the deliverable describes the importance of engaging the broader citizen science community to achieve the objectives of ECS, who and how will be engaged and what this means. It also details the steps to plan the community engagement events and how the latter will be evaluated to make sure that goals are being met and to adapt where necessary. The second part of the document presents the methodology that will be followed in the participatory co-design process to select and develop new services for the platform. The different phases of the yearly co-design cycle are presented as well as associated activities.

The document is presented in the following order:

Section 1 introduces the current plan for the community engagement events. Section 2 focuses on the co-design process and methodology that will be followed for the selection and development of new platform services. Section 3 highlights some aspects related to inclusivity in the activities described. Inclusivity in ECS is to be applied in the project in a cross-cutting way and is therefore also relevant for the activities detailed in this document. Section 4 addresses evaluation and co-evaluation in said activities. Finally, section 5 gathers some concluding remarks and next steps. The annexes include a variety of co-design activities to be carried out in the project, both thought specifically to fit the needs of the co-design process of ECS and extracted from the Cos4Cloud co-design methodology (Guasch et al. 2022).

Introduction

Within the last decade, citizen science has experienced a rapid growth in Europe – and beyond – and it has become an important mode of research and innovation. Citizen science practitioners have realised that there is a common need to share experiences and practices in different aspects of any citizen science project, from engaging citizens to data collection and analysis, and the dissemination of results, in order to ensure that the European citizen science community learns from each others' experiences. Citizen science has gained recognition across policy, research funding organisations, scientists, civic society organisations, NGOs, and those working in the interface of science and society. However, citizen science uptake and acceptance across disciplines, actors and institutions is still limited. Coupled to this is the need to make sure that funding agencies really understand the dimensions and amount of human and financial resources any citizen science activity requires. More and more citizen science associations, national, regional and international citizen science platforms exist that promote and advocate for citizen science and help to build networks of citizen science practitioners and establish links. One of the aims of the ECS project is to create a long-lasting European citizen science community.

WP2 of ECS, “Strengthening links and collaboration”, has the overall objective to strengthen and expand the citizen science community. The WP aims to gather existing and new actors in citizen science in the journey of co-creation. The specific objectives of the WP are twofold: on the one hand, to run various community engagement activities and nominate ambassadors for citizen science all over Europe and, on the other hand, to enlarge and enhance the eu-citizen.science platform with new tools, services and resources, and connect it with national citizen science infrastructure.

The current deliverable, D2.1 “Plan for the community co-creation activities”, focuses on the activities of tasks 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3: on building the European citizen science community of the future, selecting the new services for the eu-citizen.science platform in a participatory way, and co-designing and developing new services for the platform. These tasks run almost across the whole project and are related in the following way:

T2.1 aims to expand and strengthen the citizen science community (generally speaking) building upon existing communities such as the members of ECSA and the users of the eu-citizen.science platform, and taking advantage of the involvement of networks in the project such as Public Libraries 2030 and the Marie Curie Alumni Association. The core of T2.1 will be a series of engagement activities throughout the project that ECS has named “community engagement events” (at least 25 at European and national level) and workshops with the ECSA working groups (at least one per year and in parallel to the community engagement events). Part of this task is the setting up of a network of 28 ECS Ambassadors (EU-27 + UK) that will support the engagement of the affiliated entities in ECS in the national events and promote the use of the eu-citizen.science platform. The ECS community built in T2.1 will actively participate in the definition and development of new citizen science tools and services in T2.2 and T2.3.

T2.2 is on the participatory selection of new services for the eu-citizen.science platform. The objective of this task is to identify and prioritise the development of at least five new services to be offered to the citizen science community and integrated in the eu-citizen.science platform. An updated version of the platform will be released once a year. T2.3 concentrates on the co-design and development of said new services for the platform and is therefore closely interlinked to T2.2. The co-design and development of new services and platform enhancements will be based on the community contributions of T2.2 and will follow the co-design methodology implemented in the [Cos4Cloud project](#) (H2020 project funded under GA nr. 863463). Co-design workshops

will take place as part of this task to account for the needs of the community, including service leaders and other interested stakeholders, thus enlarging the community of users and developers.

Therefore, T2.2 and T2.3 can be thought together as different but complementary phases of the implementation of new platform services: first the selection, then the development of the services. The broader community built and developed in T2.1 will be engaged in the activities of T2.2 and T2.3 to develop the services. The activities in all three tasks feed into and influence each other, and will develop side by side during the course of the project with each of the community engagement events and iterations to develop new platform services.

The aim of this deliverable is to provide a plan that informs and provides the rationale for the activities in T2.1, T2.2 and T2.3 mentioned and serves as a guide and reference document to plan said activities. As the first rounds of community engagement events and co-design activities are carried out over the next months, the plan will be adapted and further refined as needed.

Section 1 of this deliverable introduces the current plan for the community engagement events. Section 2 focuses on the co-design process and methodology that will be followed for the selection and development of new platform services. Section 3 highlights some aspects related to inclusivity in the activities described. Inclusivity in ECS is to be applied in the project in a cross-cutting way and is therefore also relevant for the activities detailed in this document. Section 4 addresses evaluation and co-evaluation in said activities. Finally, section 5 gathers some concluding remarks and next steps. The annexes include a variety of co-design activities to be carried out in the project, both thought specifically to fit the needs of the co-design process of ECS and extracted from the Cos4Cloud co-design methodology (Guasch et al. 2022).

Project Background

Project details

Project full title and acronym: European Citizen Science (ECS)

Grant Agreement no.: 101058509

Call: HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01

Topic: HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-60 (A capacity-building and brokering network to make citizen science an integral part of the European Research Area)

Type of action: CSA

Start date: 01/08/2022

End date: 31/07/2026

Number of participants in the Consortium: 12 beneficiaries and 9 Affiliated Entities

Project description

The overall objective of ECS is to widen and strengthen the European Citizen Science community through capacity building and awareness raising activities such as the creation of a European Citizen Science Academy and the establishment of a network of 28 ECS Ambassadors. ECS will capitalise on EU-funded actions such as the [eu-citizen.science platform](#) and [Cos4Cloud](#) to support links and collaboration between members of the

European Citizen Science community, who will be involved in the co-design and co-creation of a large variety of services, strategic priorities, training opportunities and policy recommendations. A key focus is on inclusivity, which will be achieved through dedicated actions such as engaging libraries affiliated to the Public Libraries 2030 network to attract underrepresented publics, as well as ad-hoc support to countries/regions lacking citizen science networks, platforms and policy recognition.

ECS will create extensive capacity building opportunities by engaging in particular excellent researchers in a variety of disciplines, for example through the involvement of the Marie Curie Alumni Association, and emerging Horizon Europe Missions, Clusters, and wider ERA activities, to allow easy access for newcomers in citizen science activities. ECS is committed to push modern science towards open science as its modus operandi by providing open collaborative spaces where citizen scientists can familiarise with the concept of "open and FAIR data with open and FAIR tools" and get actively engaged, while connecting with existing e-infrastructures such as EOSC through the collaborative development of data/metadata services. The engagement of the Citizen Science Global Partnership will guarantee wide international cooperation. These efforts will result in a number of key scientific, societal and policy impacts which will strongly contribute to securing Europe's global position as a leader in citizen science throughout the entire research and innovation system.

The six specific objectives of ECS are:

- **Objective 1:** Empower the European citizen science community through co-design and co-creation
- **Objective 2:** Strengthen the links and collaboration between existing citizen science initiatives
- **Objective 3:** Increase the participation of citizens from all walks of life in citizen science through an inclusive approach
- **Objective 4:** Build the capacity to conduct excellent research and innovation through citizen science
- **Objective 5:** Raise awareness, support and mainstream citizen science among new actors, new territories and scientific fields
- **Objective 6:** Better align data infrastructures to the needs of citizen science, and improve open science practices employed by citizen science initiatives

Project Consortium

The ECS consortium is composed of 12 Beneficiaries and 9 Affiliated Entities, members of ECSA, covering 15 countries. The consortium is truly interdisciplinary and complementary in terms of expertise and is a perfect fit to reach the objectives and impact required by this call. The beneficiaries unite expertise in citizen science (ECSA, UP, MfN, Ibercivis, SfC, CSIC) and co-creation (SD, SfC), platform and community development (Ibercivis, CSIC, ECSA), coupled with experience in inclusion and diversity (PL2030, SfC, SD, ZSI) as well as leading expertise in data infrastructure and ethics (CSIC). All of the above combined with recognised competence in impact assessment (ZSI) and a huge geographical coverage (MCAA, ECSA, PL2030) makes the ECS team a perfect fit for successful project implementation.

In addition to the 12 partners, ECS consortium consists of nine ECSA Affiliated Entities. The nine Affiliated Entities and NILU (due to administrative reasons, NILU is included in the proposal as partner but their role is the same as that of Affiliated Entities) represent a diversity of stakeholders such as SMEs, NGO, public body, museum, research organisation and university – all with expertise in citizen science. They come from 10 different countries and were selected through a public call for ECSA members.

Table 1. Participants in the ECS Consortium – 12 beneficiaries and 9 Affiliated Entities.

Acronym	Role ¹	Participant	Country	Logo
ECSA	COO	European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) ECSA E.V.	Germany	European Citizen Science Association
W2L	AE	Web2Learn	Greece	Web2Learn Open. social learning
ULEI	AE	Universiteit Leiden	Netherlands	citizen science lab
ULHT/CeD	AE	Cooperativa de Formação e Animação Cultural CRL	Portugal	UNIVERSIDADE LUSÓFONA
TCD	AE	The Provost, Fellows, Foundation Scholars & the Other Members of Board, of the College of the Holy & Undivided Trinity of Queen Elizabeth Near Dublin (Trinity College)	Ireland	Trinity College Dublin Coláiste na Tríonóide, Baile Átha Cliath The University of Dublin
NORDECO	AE	Nordisk Fond for Miljø og Udvikling	Denmark	NORDECO Nordic Agency for Development and Ecology
MOFET INSTITUTE	AE	The MOFET Institute - The School For The Research And Development Of Programs In Teacher Training And Education At Colleges	Israel	The MOFET Institute Research, Curriculum and Program Development for Teacher Educators
FGC	AE	Fondazione Grosseto Cultura	Italy	MUSEO DI STORIA NATURALE DELLA MAREMMA
IGN	AE	Institute of Geonics Of The AS CR, V.V.I.	Czech Republic	ÚGN
BWI	AE	Blue World Institute	Croatia	BLUE WORLD INSTITUTE
SD	BEN	Stickydot SRL	Belgium	STICKY DOT
SfC	BEN	Science for Change, SL	Spain	Science for Change

¹ COO stands for coordinator; AE stands for affiliated entity; BE stands for beneficiary.

IBERCIVIS	BEN	Fundación Ibercivis	Spain	
CSIC	BEN	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC)	Spain	
MFN	BEN	Museum für Naturkunde - Leibniz-Institut für Evolutions- und Biodiversitätsforschung, Berlin	Germany	
ZSI	BEN	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation GMBH	Austria	
MCAA	BEN	Marie Curie Alumni Association	Belgium	
PL2030	BEN	Public Libraries 2030	Belgium	
UP	BEN	Université Paris Cité	France	
NILU	BEN	Nilu Stiftelsen Norsk Institutt For Luftforskning (NILU)	Norway	
NMC	BEN	Nordlicht Management Consultant	Germany	

Project Work Packages

The ECS project comprises nine WPs understood as building blocks that are structured to deliver the outputs efficiently, ensuring the highest return on the resources that are invested (see Figure 1 below). All WPs are closely linked, thus running throughout the entire duration of the project.

List of WPs:

WP1 – Project management and coordination

- WP2 – Strengthening links and collaboration
- WP3 – Enhancing digital skills for FAIR and open science communities
- WP4 – European citizen science academy
- WP5 – Boosting inclusion and diversity for mainstreaming citizen science
- WP6 – Communication and outreach for the global citizen science community
- WP7 – Policy impacts and recommendations
- WP8 – Impact Pathways Assessment
- WP9 – Ethics requirements

Figure 1. ECS work package structure.

WP1 is dedicated to project management and coordination with the EC. WP2 and WP3 focus on collaboration and openness aspects of the ECS community, to lay the ground for its wider activities. WP2 has a greater focus on bringing together the European Citizen Science community, including enhancing the online services of the eu-citizen.science platform and supporting networks Europe-wide. WP3 focuses on enhancing digital skills and data services towards FAIR and open practices. Both WP2 and WP3 are supported by a dedicated effort to provide training and capacity building through the European Citizen Science Academy in WP4. To ensure inclusion and diversity in the process of mainstreaming citizen science, WP5 is dedicated to this mission. WP6 is aimed at communication and outreach, and international collaboration, while WP7 is dedicated to policy impacts and uptake of emerging recommendations at national, European, and global levels. WP8 closely monitors the envisioned impact pathways of all WPs, providing evidence for the achievement of the expected outputs and outcomes. Finally, WP9 is dedicated to ethics requirements.

1. Community engagement in ECS

1.1. *The importance of engaging the community in the project*

The overall objective of ECS is to widen and strengthen the European citizen science community through capacity building and awareness raising activities. Moreover, three out of the six specific objectives of ECS mentioned in the previous section aim at building the community, strengthening links and collaboration, and increasing participation, as detailed below.

- **Objective 1:** Empower the European citizen science community through co-design and co-creation

All members of the European citizen science community, from newcomers to experienced practitioners, have a role to play in shaping the community, its needs and what it can offer. This empowerment process is key to community engagement in the project: not only do community members have a say on all aspects of the work done in ECS, but they also take part in its development. As a result, they feel empowered to support, advocate for, implement and share citizen science in their local environments.

- **Objective 2:** Strengthen the links and collaboration between existing citizen science initiatives

The eu-citizen.science platform represents the most up-to-date collection of initiatives, best practices and tools in citizen science in Europe, serving as a catalyst for learning, competence development, discussion and collaboration. ECS leverages and strengthens the eu-citizen.science platform, while promoting interactions with EU-funded projects and harnessing resources and outputs from citizen science initiatives. Through these actions, ECS achieves an optimisation of knowledge sharing and exploitation of results at European level and beyond, including interactions with global citizen science networks.

- **Objective 3:** Increase the participation of citizens from all walks of life in citizen science through an inclusive approach

Following Principle Two: Leave No One Behind of the United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goals, which is committed to reducing inequalities and vulnerabilities, ECS' quintuple helix engagement approach contributes to democratising science by involving diverse publics, and underrepresented ones in particular. This is achieved through a series of cross-cutting actions throughout the whole project.

In the context of citizen science, communication, dissemination, engagement and outreach are related concepts, but they have distinct differences in their meanings and applications.

Communication involves the exchange of information and ideas, and includes clear and transparent communication of project goals, research questions, methods, and findings. Communication in citizen science also includes providing feedback to participants on their contributions and the impact of the project. In citizen science, communication plays a crucial role as it is required to recruit, engage and motivate participants (Rüfenacht et al. 2021). It is also important for sharing research findings (dissemination) and teaching participants about the project's focus and the scientific process (Veeckman et al. 2019).

Dissemination commonly takes place towards the end of a project when sharing research results and findings with a wider audience and interested parties, beyond those that participated in the project, with the aim of others making use of the results. In science, including citizen science, the process of sharing research results is usually a one-way communication, often achieved through the publication of research findings in scientific journals, presentations at conferences, or briefings for policy-makers (Rüfenacht et al. 2021). Dissemination is

important for making research accessible and relevant to a broader audience, and for creating a feedback loop between citizens and scientists.

Engagement refers to the process of actively involving citizens and other stakeholders in scientific research or in a particular project in a meaningful way. Engagement often involves creating opportunities for citizens to actively participate in a scientific project, contribute their expertise, and take ownership of the research (Bonney et al. 2009; Kasperowski et al. 2017). Such opportunities typically include but are not limited to: co-design of research questions, mapping of needs and stakeholders, collection, analysis, and interpretation of data; co-creation of messages, channels and formats in communication strategies and any sort of decision-making regarding a scientific project. Engagement is a two-way conversation between project or activity organisers and participants.

The *National Coordination Center for Public Engagement* defines public engagement as "the myriad of ways in which the activity and benefits of higher education and research can be shared with the public. Engagement is by definition a two-way process, involving interaction and listening, with the goal of generating mutual benefit" (National Coordination Center for Public Engagement n.d.).

From an historical perspective – albeit brief – the term **engagement** entered our language with the transition from the so-called *deficit model* of science communication to the *dialogue model* and finally to the *participative model*. Citizen science represents the highest expression of the participatory model as it not only actively involves people but makes them protagonists of the scientific process. In the vision in which public participation is a key element, the public itself becomes a partner; experts and non-experts look each other in the eyes at the same level and work collaboratively towards a common goal.

Outreach, defined as "an effort to bring services or information to people where they live or spend time" by the Cambridge Dictionary (Cambridge University Press 2023), involves, in this case, the effort made by scientists or science organisations to reach out to potential participants and stakeholders to increase awareness about the project and attract participants. Outreach is a method of communication and, as such, can involve promoting the project to the public, building partnerships with community organisations, or collaborating with educators to involve students in the project. Outreach is important for expanding the pool of potential participants and building relationships with stakeholders.

In summary, engagement focuses on actively involving citizens or participants to generate mutual benefit, communication focuses on exchanging information, dissemination focuses on sharing research findings with a wider audience, and outreach focuses on reaching out to potential participants and stakeholders. These concepts are all important for carrying out effective citizen science, and a successful citizen science project or initiative should ideally involve a combination of these elements. This is also the case with ECS.

ECS will organise activities taking the aforementioned concepts into account and considering them as parts of a dynamic process. The ultimate goal of such a process will be engaging new audiences in the broader citizen science community in Europe.

While all mentioned elements are important to achieve the objectives of ECS, a distinction between the different activities and aims is in order to better and more effectively plan the wide range of activities in the project. The **community engagement events organised in ECS** will have the **main goal of building, and enlarging the citizen science community in Europe** by entering into dialogue with different audiences and or **strengthening the links and collaboration between existing citizen science initiatives** by actively involving participants in events. The communication and dissemination activities in the project aim to maximise the

impact of the project, increase its visibility, and ensure that project outputs reach a wide audience and the relevant stakeholders. The community engagement events will go hand in hand with the communication and dissemination activities in the ECS project.

In this sense, ECS will make a distinction between these activities: e.g. a presentation of the ECS project in the framework of a conference to communicate about the project and disseminate its results to a wider audience will continue to count as communication and dissemination activity, as is usually the case, and as part of T6.2 “Communication tools and events” of ECS; on the other hand, the organisation of a festival, a workshop, a world café, etc. with the main aim to build and strengthen the community, will count towards the community engagement events as part of T2.1 “Co-creating the European Citizen Science community of the future”.

1.2. Stakeholder engagement

To strengthen the community and broaden the scope of intervention of ECS and citizen science in Europe, ECS will organise a series of community engagement events – at least 25, at national and European level – targeting different audiences and stakeholders as defined in the ECS ‘Communication and Dissemination Plan’ (D6.1). Additional stakeholders have been added to the list below with respect to D6.1:

Academia: citizen science practitioners, career scientists, researchers at different career levels new to citizen science, Science Shops, members of higher education institutions, universities and research centres.

Citizens and the public: citizen scientists, newcomers in citizen science including, young people, the elderly, women, citizens from diverse socio-economic backgrounds.

Civil society: non-profit organisations, citizen science associations, citizen science networks, representatives of associations (museum associations, science and research associations, science communication associations), activist organisations, grassroots movements, local communities, community centres, Science Shops, maker communities, special interest groups, charities, libraries, cultural institutions, public engagement organisations.

Policy-makers: regional and national policy-makers, members of foundations and funding agencies, members of EU institutions and units (e.g. EU Missions, Green Deal, the relevant DGs, European Parliament).

Private sector: small and medium enterprises, start-ups, social innovators and entrepreneurs, open source innovators, Living Labs and FabLabs, representatives of industry associations at regional, national and EU levels.

Research translation and intermediaries: organisations such as Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs), incubators and accelerators of research-based companies, science innovation centres etc.

Formal and non-formal education: citizen science educators, formal and non-formal education communities, students, school teachers, public engagement departments, natural history and science museums, science centres, visitor centres, etc.

Media and media operators are essential mediators with society, an important source of visibility and a reference point for policy makers. Even if it is beyond the scope of the project to organise a professional press office, the utmost care will be taken in making the media aware of the project’s achievements, stories, important events and publications. Each project partner will seek to maintain contact with the media in their country within the scope of their possibilities and local and national connections.

It is worth mentioning here the **use of the term community** in the project and in D2.1 more specifically. We often refer to the “European citizen science community” or the “community of citizen science in Europe”. We broadly understand the term citizen science community as encompassing those that are involved in citizen

science in some capacity. However, we recognise that there is a wide range of communities at the core of current citizen science developments. Besides strong continental communities (i.e. the [European](#), [U.S.](#), [Latin American](#), [African](#), [Asian](#) and [Australian](#) associations of citizen science, and the [Citizen Science Global Partnership](#)), a variety of European national citizen science associations and networks exist, and groups have formed around specific interests and topics, such as the over a dozen different [ECSA working groups](#). Communities of developers often join forces towards open data sharing and infrastructures, while the EPA Network of the European Environment Agency has an [interest group dedicated to citizen science](#). As noted, several EU countries, regions, and cities have growing communities, supported by public funding but also bottom-up and citizen-led initiatives. The community of citizen science is not homogeneous, nor is expected to be. ECS aims to link the above-mentioned communities, and more, to create and support a European one, with strong international links.

Based on the extensive list of audiences and stakeholders relevant to the ECS project, an iterative stakeholder mapping will take place to **identify relevant actors and stakeholders to involve in T2.1 activities** (community engagement events) **as well as in the co-design activities of T2.2 and T2.3** described in section 2. As we organise activities in WP2 and reach out to and engage with targeted audiences and stakeholders, we will see who we are more easily reaching, who we should be making a greater effort to reach and engage and how to do that, etc. Stakeholder engagement might look different at different points in the project. Therefore, **reflecting about stakeholder engagement accompanied by a thought-out stakeholder mapping** will be a recurrent task across the project. The partners and affiliated entities will be involved in contributing to this reflection and stakeholder mapping. It is worth noting here that D2.1 of the EU-Citizen.Science project² (EU-Citizen.Science Consortium 2019) provides an incredibly valuable foundation to continue developing the ECS stakeholder mapping.

Following the overall objective of the project of **widening and strengthening the European citizen science community**, the community engagement events in the project will also follow this and focus on *widening* when the emphasis is put on reaching out to new audiences and potential stakeholders, and on *strengthening* when the focus lies on consolidating and reinforcing current links in the community. This distinction will also inform the content and format of the community engagement events.

Widening, however, especially refers to involving underrepresented countries (low participation rates in FP7 and H2020 projects, European Research Executive Agency (2023)) in the Research and Innovation effort. Widening the community of citizen science Europe is one of the aims of the ECS project in WP2 but also beyond that in WP5 and tasks dedicated to enlarging the geographical scope of citizen science initiatives.

As part of T2.1, a network of 28 CS Ambassadors (EU-27 + UK) will be set up to support community building and the engagement of the affiliated entities in ECS in the national and local events and promote the use of the eu-citizen.science platform. CS Ambassadors will also promote, leverage and expand the eu-citizen.science platform with national initiatives and resources. The network of Ambassadors aims at raising awareness about citizen science and spreading and strengthening citizen science in countries where it is still not supported or is not established. CS Ambassadors will advocate for citizen science among key stakeholders identified in WP7

² D2.1 from EU-Citizen.Science maps and describes the key actors and interested parties whose support and involvement would ensure the success of the EU-Citizen.Science platform. This was accomplished by systematically reviewing the individuals and organisations who play a key role in citizen science activities in general, who were likely to also become the core users of the EU-Citizen.Science platform in particular (EU-Citizen.Science Consortium 2019).

dedicated to 'Policy impacts and recommendations'. Further, Ambassadors will promote citizen science amongst research organisations nationally.

To exemplify: stakeholders, projects and initiatives with whom ECS is already in contact and where links are established (*strengthening*) are the ecosystem of projects on citizen science funded by the SwafS programme under Horizon 2020, the citizen science projects and initiatives taking part in the ECS Collaboration Group as part of T2.5 in the project (including ECS's sister project [IMPETUS](#), ERA-61 call winner), national and regional citizen science networks, associations and platforms (mainly in Europe, but also beyond), the ECSA working groups, and the network of educators that is being established in WP4 of ECS.

Part of *widening* the community could be: reaching out to Science Shops and the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) to engage with them more actively, forging connections with Ecsite to open up to the science centres and science communication community, establishing links with Scientix to reach out to schools and educators, connecting with the networks of all partners and affiliated entities in the project, supporting the advocacy work of CS Ambassadors in widening countries in collaboration with WP5 and WP7.

1.3. Community engagement events

ECS's community engagement events will be designed and implemented following the principles outlined in the ECS 'Communication and Dissemination Plan' (D6.1). They will reach out to a variety of stakeholders both within and outside the citizen science community; the objectives, listed below, have a value far beyond the benefit of the project itself:

- **Get visibility.** The public and stakeholders are often not aware of the existing citizen science projects and opportunities to participate, therefore **engagement events** could increase visibility both locally and sometimes nationally, and even internationally.
- **Get support.** The scientific community cannot pursue its mission without **the support of society**, which provides direct financing, or indirectly, legislation that facilitates scientific and technological research.
- **Gain trust.** In the absence of an attitude of trust in the scientific community, both facts and figures may be challenged by large groups of citizens, including policy-makers. **Gaining trust and being considered reliable partners** require a careful and continuous communication commitment.
- **Improve governance.** There are complex and controversial issues on which citizens are called to decide upon together with policy-makers, stakeholders and the scientific community.
- **Support recruitment.** Engaging various stakeholders in our project contributes **to creating a positive image of scientists as professionals**, in order to attract new generations of researchers.
- **Foster information and education.** The citizen science approach can support educators and learners, facilitate exchange of knowledge in both directions, and make learners active partners in participating in authentic scientific research.

1.3.1. Steps to plan the community engagement events

These steps are essential to think about and plan community engagement events³:

³ "Community engagement events" is taken here to include not only the planned 25 community engagement events but also the yearly workshops planned with ECSA WGs for ease of use.

Define the goals of the activities

What is the purpose of the activity? For example, increasing awareness of citizen science, bringing in newcomers to citizen science, strengthening links between members that are already part of the community, recruiting potential participants in other project tasks, etc. Think also about the expectations that participants might have taking part in such activities. Offer different ways of participating in community engagement events to cater to a diverse audience.

Identify and define the target audience

Who do we want to reach through these events? This is closely linked to the point above. Here it might be helpful to consider involving existing communities or specific target groups and individuals that have already participated in other project activities (INCENTIVE Consortium 2022).

It is crucial to understand the local context and communities where we want to deploy ECS activities. For instance, one of the project objectives is to address underrepresented groups and engage them in citizen science. We assume that everyone wants to be involved in citizen science. However, it is important to reflect where and how it makes sense for them to get involved and ideally reach out to these groups and stakeholders first to ask directly.

Actively listen for opportunities

ECS will set up an apparatus based on subscriptions to mailing lists/newsletters and monitoring of relevant keywords in social media in order to keep track of upcoming events, opportunities and relevant actors that may have not been identified previously, so initial lists such as the ones shown in table 2 and table 3 below will be updated dynamically during the project, and so will be the plan of activities. It is expected that all partners involved in this task proactively contribute ideas and suggestions of already-existing, wider events.

Plan the activity or event

Adapt the activity (and the methodology) to align to the purpose of the activity and the target audience. What kind of activity will take place? Will it be more hands-on, a workshop, a world café...? Will guests be invited to provide additional resources or expertise? A fundamental step here (and in planning the communication and outreach strategy that accompanies the community engagement events more generally) is to identify the barriers and 'non-motivations' to the participation of the target audience in citizen science and subsequently, to develop some strategies to overcome them. This might be especially helpful in the case of wishing to engage underrepresented groups.

Plan the logistics around the activity or event

The activity should take place in locations that are easily accessible to the target audience and at times when potential participants are able to attend. Online activities also need careful planning in terms of logistics and what platforms, formats and tools to use, since some of these risk exclusion. It is important to provide adequate supporting material for the activities.

In terms of communication, it is important to adopt an inclusive and understandable language in alignment with the target audience. Guidelines and tips on this are included in the 'Communication and Dissemination Plan' of ECS (D6.1).

Promote the event and invite participants

Advertise the community engagement events through social media, local newspapers, flyers, depending on the audience(s) to be reached. Encourage participants to bring friends and family, and offer incentives for attendees.

Evaluate the events

Evaluate the events and activities carried out through feedback forms or surveys from participants and guests to assess what worked well and what could be improved. Evaluate internally within the organising team how the event went and if its objectives were met. Use the information gathered to plan future events.

Communication and follow-up

Stay in touch with the participants, acknowledge their contributions and provide opportunities to get involved in upcoming events and in the project when and where possible. Since the goal of T2.1 is to build the European citizen science community of the future, continued communication and follow-up will be of utmost importance to build connections and strengthen existing links.

The core team involved in carrying out the community engagement events will focus on planning, facilitation/engagement, communication, and evaluation of the events and will be composed of task leader ECSA and contributing partners SD, SfC, Ibercivis, MfN, UP, CSIC, and MCAA.

1.3.2. Types of community engagement events

As the public and stakeholders are many and varied, even the media and places where the engagement events are carried out are very different in nature. There are many possible tools and scenarios available, from the more traditional ones to the more unexpected and more appropriate to highlight the potential of citizen science.

Ideas and suggestions for community engagement events are, for example, stakeholder workshops, webinars and discussions on topics of common interest among stakeholders, world cafés, roundtable discussions, focus groups, (small) conferences and festivals, an interactive display, community challenges and friendly competitions, etc. The events can be organised, on one hand, as satellite events or along already existing (external) events of relevance for the citizen science community such as the EU Research and Innovation Days (EU R&I Days), the Green Week, the Citizen Science month, the European Researchers' Night, the European Open Science Forum, events organised by national citizen science platforms and associations, etc. Some examples of these are provided in table 2. Especially when aiming to *widen* the community and reach out to newcomers to citizen science, it will be important to identify key events attended by our target stakeholders and communities. On the other hand, ECS will organise community engagement events from scratch; sometimes linked or in parallel to other events in the project to maximise impact and reach a wider audience. Partners and affiliated entities involved in the task will regularly share ideas or be asked for input on events that they are organising – both as part of ECS and in the framework of their organisation – to explore new opportunities. Some ideas by partners contributing to the task have been collected and shared in table 3. Already completed or planned engagement events are displayed in table 4.

In November 2022, a recurring monthly meeting was set up between WPs 2 and 5 to facilitate the coordination of ECS activities throughout the project, ensure an intersectional inclusive perspective in citizens' and quintuple helix stakeholder involvement, and co-create the ECS community of the future (T2.1). These as well as monthly WP2 meetings will be the places to gather ideas, discuss and plan upcoming community engagement events.

Table 2. Examples of various types of engagement events.

TYPE OF EVENT	DESCRIPTION	REFERENCES Examples, comments
Forum or community event	A forum is a place, situation, or group in which people exchange ideas and discuss issues, especially important public issues.	https://livingknowledge.org/events/regular-events/
Science festivals	Science festivals celebrate science and technology by bringing them to squares and public spaces with the same freshness, flair and emotions of a music or art festival. Born in the UK, they have been exported all over the world and today hundreds of them are organised every year. Surely there will be one taking place near the place you live or the institution where you work. Science festivals offer a great variety of events, from conferences and round tables also with the presence of famous stars, workshops, experiment sessions, games, music, all in a very informal context. Each festival has its own recipe and specialties.	https://www.isbglasgow.com/18-biggest-science-fairs-and-festivals-in-the-world/
European Researchers' Night	It is a Europe-wide public event, which displays the diversity of science and its impact on citizens' daily lives in fun, inspiring ways.	https://www.researchersnight.eu/
School/education activities	Any kind of engaging activities with school children based on the citizen science approach.	Our organisations may have a public engagement program with schools and ECS can be included in the existing programs. Check whether your organisation are part of the European Children's Universities Association (EUCU.NET)
Open days	An event in which an organisation (such as a school or company) invites the public to visit in order to see the things that happen there.	Check whether our organisations organise such events and join to present ECS with a lab, an interactive talk, a citizen science initiative, etc.
Public talks	A public lecture employed for informing, engaging, educating the public in the arts and sciences.	If we happen to hold a citizen science-themed public seminar, let's not forget to include ECS and its services and products,

		whatever the audience the seminar is aimed at.
Local/community forum on a specific topic	It is a place, situation, or group in which people exchange ideas and discuss issues.	Each partner can select a topic locally relevant and organised a public forum involving a school or a community.
FameLab or similar competitions	FameLab is the largest, public facing, science communication competition and training programme in the world. Created by Cheltenham Festivals in 2005, it is now performed in many European countries.	Check whether your town hosts a Famelab event and take part (only for young researchers).
Pub quizzes or similar events	The most famous one is the Pint of Science, an annual science festival that aims to communicate contemporary scientific developments to the public by bringing scientists to pubs, cafés and other public places to share their research and findings.	ECS partners can organise an event in one of their local bars.
BioBlitz or similar events	It is an intense period of biological surveying in an attempt to record all the living species within a designated area. Groups of scientists, naturalists and volunteers conduct an intensive field study over a continuous time period.	Any one of the partners organise a BioBlitz or a similar event?

Table 3. Events organised by ECS partners to link or couple ECS community engagement events.

PARTNER	EVENT	NETWORKS REACHED OR WITH ACCESS TO	BENEFIT TO THE NETWORKS	IDEAS FOR TYPES OF EVENTS
ECSA	ECSA Conference 2024 and 2026 (maybe the latter after the end of the project) ECSA webinars (monthly)	ECSA members, eu-citizen.science users, other EU-funded projects & their partners	Sharing best practice in CS mainly in Europe, match-making to strengthening links (similar topics/aims), learning about the platform and how to use it, learning about ECS opportunities and how to benefit from them (new platform services, training, sessions on inclusion,...)	
SfC	4 Capacity building sessions as part of WP5	ECSA WGs, library staff, ECS Ambassadors	Promote inclusivity and empowerment of all citizens in Europe in citizen science projects	

Ibercivis	Event to launch new services for the ECS platform (once a year).	Community around the ECS platform	Strengthen participation each year and increase the community around the platform.	Face-to-face/online workshops on the project, platform, the different participatory processes of the project, the citizen science academy...
Ibercivis	Usually at least one public event at national level per year.	Spanish citizen science community	Increasing the scope of the ECS project	Posters, participation/moderation of round tables and in open discussions...
UP	Ambition to set up a quarterly meet-up at the LPI (in-person) for individuals engaged or wanting to know more about CS (e.g. a community meet up to informally ask questions and meet with peers).	Access to a network of researchers via the University of Paris. Reach out to other universities, other organisations involved in the topic of 'science & society' within France & Paris, public libraries, and museums (can also be included in organisations involved in 'science & society' category).	Raising awareness about what citizen science is and developing training material to match the needs of a wide range of actors.	Quarterly meet-up in person Need to understand where our outreach will be.
MCAA	ECS Satellite event as part of MCAA Annual Conference	MCAA Young Researchers		

Table 4. Completed or planned engagement events (at least 25 over the course of the project).

EVENT	DESCRIPTION	WHEN AND WHERE
Learning Planet Festival	A public workshop to experience citizen science organised by UP on the occasion of the International Day of #Education, 24 January. Both in English and French.	Paris, 27 January 2023 (completed)
Lange Nacht der Wissenschaft	ECSCA will organise an engagement activity in and with the Museum für Naturkunde ,	Berlin, 17 June 2023 (planned)

	within this big public national event.	
Researchers Night 2023	ECS will join one of the existing events and present the first year of activity.	Everywhere in Europe, 29 September 2023 (working on it)

Strategic communication will contribute to increasing the impact of the project and informing about its objectives, activities and results. Some communication activities, however, can also be especially helpful in community building and can support the community engagement events. This is the case with social media campaigns. A social media campaign is a coordinated communication effort to reinforce or assist with a project, organisation or business goal using one or more social media platforms. Campaigns differ from everyday social media efforts because of their increased focus, targeting and measurability. An example of a social media campaign that was successfully run was on the event of the International Day of Women and Girls in Science (11th February), see table 5.

Table 5. Dedicated communication activities directly supporting community building.

COMMUNICATION ACTIVITY	DESCRIPTION	WHEN AND WHERE
International Day of Women and Girls in Science	A social media campaign featuring 28 short videos from the citizen science community, released from Feb 3 to Feb 11 on Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn. In collaboration with ECSA and the participation of Ibercivis and Science for Change .	On the social media channels, 3-11 February 2023 (completed)

1.3.3. Evaluation of community engagement events

The plan or methodology for community engagement in ECS is thought as dynamic allowing for changes and adaptation as the project evolves. An internal evaluation of the events carried out will help us to understand what is working and what might not be working so well so that upcoming events can be improved.

The evaluation of the community engagement events will consist of two parts:

- A satisfaction survey post-event shared with participants to ask e.g. for their motivation to attend the event, what they liked about the event, suggestions for improvement, about the length of the event (was it right?), whether they would join another ECS community engagement event or would recommend attending to a friend or colleague, etc.
- An internal evaluation by the event organising team to look at:
 - Quantitative information such as how many participants took part in the event.
 - Qualitative information:
 - Analysing both anonymised information in the registration forms (previous experience in citizen science, stakeholder group participants pertain to, etc.) and the post-event survey feedback to see whether we are reaching who we aim to be reaching and how to improve upcoming events.
 - Reflecting on what went well and what did not to learn from experience.

This will allow us to adjust the activities and approach in real-time based on the above. Feedback received from participants could be useful beyond this task and may be shared within the ECS Consortium as appropriate.

1.3.4. ECS community engagement events: guidelines for planning and communicating

This guide summarises the above sections and is intended as a tool to make the ECS community engagement events more effective and gratifying for both organisers and participants.

PHASE 1 | PLANNING

In this phase it is necessary to answer all the fundamental questions underlying any event in which you want to involve an audience or a community on a specific theme: **why, what, who, when, how**. These questions seem obvious, however very often they are not given enough importance. Investing time and thought in the preliminary phase is essential to avoid later disappointment and a waste of time and financial and human resources.

The choice of the event **title** must also be catchy and appropriate for the type of event and the type of audience. It is good to define the title at the end of the planning procedure when all elements have been clarified in the organising team.

1A. What are the most important **themes/topics** of your event?

Not only do you have to define the general theme, but also a rough storyboard, selecting the most relevant aspects for that context.

1B. Who is your intended **public**?

Everybody knows that the public, as a singular concept, does not exist. Only *publics*. For each message, we need to precisely identify the audience we want to reach. Choose among the strategic audiences and stakeholders included in the stakeholder mapping described in section 1.2 and in the *ECS Communication and dissemination plan* and learn as much as possible about them: find out their ages, gender, class and education their attitudes toward science and scientists.

1C. What do you think are the **needs of your target audience** in relation to the themes that you want to address?

Defining your target audience is not enough. Try to understand their needs and what you can do to meet them, discover possible barriers and how you can facilitate their participation.

1D. What are the **objectives** of your engagement event, and what results do you hope to obtain?

Choose one of the event engagement goals listed above as the event's primary goal. It is good to focus on a single primary objective and a few secondary objectives to maximise the effectiveness of the event. Try to be realistic.

1E. What **kind of event** do you want to set?

As said there are several kinds of engagement events, and others can be invented. Select the most appropriate one given the topic, the audience and the objectives selected. Time and money are also important constraints to take into account.

1F. What relevant professional **experience or qualifications do you or your collaborators have? Do you need any outside help?**

Graphic designers, video makers, actors, facilitators, etc. can help to make your event more successful. Don't hesitate to involve the professionals to help organise an event in the best possible way.

1G. How do you propose to evaluate the **impact of your engagement even?**

Evaluating the impact of the event means understanding whether all the objectives have been achieved. Evaluation is a large and complex subject, and this is not the context in which to develop it. It is important to remember that the evaluation is not just a list of KPIs and that it is an essential part of the communication and engagement strategy. See the section 1.3.3 *Evaluation of community engagement events* for more information.

PHASE 2 | COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

There is no universal recipe for planning the communication strategy of all types of events for any kind of audience. For each event it is necessary to develop a specific plan taking into account objectives, audience, level of engagement, kind of event, time and budget at disposal. However, some features and needs are common to all events.

Useful documents:

- A practical guide to communication in citizen science has been produced by Scivil (Veeckman et al. 2019).
- A more technical guide to develop a communication strategy by Compass, available here: <https://thecompassforsbc.org/how-to-guide/how-develop-communication-strategy>

2A. General

1. Contact the ECS communication team well in advance to plan the communication strategy (the sooner the better)
2. Always use the ECS logo, colours and visual identity style guide for all communication and dissemination materials
3. You are not alone: take advantage of possible cooperation and networking with the other partners
4. Don't forget to include the following disclaimer on all communication and dissemination materials

"The European Citizen Science (ECS) project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreement No. 101058509."

2B. Communication worksheet

When you have decided the kind of event, the date of the event, target audience, objectives, etc. described in Part 1. *Planning*, you can proceed to plan the communication strategy using the following worksheet.

Table 6. Communication worksheet.

Communication worksheet		
a. Preparation		
Starting date of the communication campaign	Depending on how the event is organised, it is necessary to establish when it is convenient to start promoting it and to establish a calendar for reinforcing the message with different means and styles.	
Target audiences of the communication campaign	It may be desirable to reach audiences also other than those defined for the event, who help to disseminate the event as a sounding board, to give support or are useful to involve. In general, it is always good to involve the local media.	
Communication partners	Are there other ECS partners involved? Or any external organisations (NGOs, members of impacted communities, industry leaders, etc.) who may be able to help reach your target audiences?	
Spokespeople	Who will be quoted in the communication material (ideally not more than three people)? Who will be available for interviews?	
Materials	What materials will be prepared (e.g., press release, social media posts, blog post, non-technical fact sheet)? Who will draft them?	
b. Messaging		
Key words or elements	Top 1-3 important and key words or elements that helps to frame and describe the event and create engagement	
Pitch	3-4 sentences combining the above. They could be used to prepare leaflets, invitations, stories for blogs and social media channels, press releases.	
c. Distribution		
What	Who	When
Social media channel stories	Social media manager of your organisation and ECS	
Leaflet (or similar material)		
Press release	Press officer	
Mailing list invitation		
Other		

2. Co-design methodology in ECS

2.1. Introduction to co-design methodologies

As the team responsible for WP2, with some experience in participatory and citizen science projects, we strongly believe in the importance of using a methodology for participatory co-design processes. A well-structured and systematic methodology not only provides a clear structure for the project, but it also ensures that the co-design process is transparent, participatory, and inclusive. It provides a roadmap for the project and helps to ensure that all stakeholders are involved in the design process and that their input is taken into account.

One of the key benefits of using a defined methodology is that it helps to ensure the validity and reliability of the co-design process. A structured methodology ensures that the co-design process is consistent and follows a set of established principles, which helps to minimise the risk of bias and ensures that the design process is transparent and accountable (Ospina-Pinillos et al., 2019). This is particularly important in citizen science projects, where a wide range of stakeholders may be involved, and where it is essential to ensure that all perspectives are taken into account.

In fact, the application of co-design methodologies in projects involving representatives of the quintuple helix can generate important benefits. Firstly, co-design allows the different actors involved in the project to contribute their knowledge and experience to achieve more effective and complete solutions. This translates into improved project quality by identifying problems and opportunities that might not otherwise have been considered and designing solutions that are better suited to the needs of all stakeholders.

Secondly, co-design promotes the inclusion and participation of the stakeholders of the quintuple helix in the design and development of the project, which increases their commitment and sense of ownership. The active participation of affected people allows them to express their needs and concerns, which contributes to creating solutions that are more adapted to local realities and context-specific challenges (Sanders and Stappers, 2008).

Moreover, the application of co-design methodologies strengthens the relationships between the actors of the quintuple helix, as it promotes collaboration and teamwork. This collaboration can create an atmosphere of trust and constructive dialogue, which favours the implementation of the project and the achievement of common objectives.

In addition, co-design can foster the generation of new ideas and innovative solutions. Collaboration between the different actors involved in the project can stimulate creativity and critical thinking, which can be especially important in projects involving emerging technologies or requiring different solutions.

Finally, the application of co-design methodologies can contribute to making projects more sustainable by considering not only technical and economic aspects, but also social, environmental and cultural aspects. This holistic perspective can ensure that the project has a positive long-term impact and that potential negative impacts can be anticipated and managed (Campisi et al., 2018).

One relevant example of a methodology for participatory co-design processes is the co-design methodology (Guasch et al., 2022) developed within the Cos4Cloud project (European Horizon 2020 project; Grant Agreement nr. 863463). This methodology provides a structured approach to the co-design of technological solutions to address needs of citizen science projects. The methodology involves a range of stakeholders in the design process, including users, experts, and representatives from relevant organisations, and leverages a set of principles, activities and guidelines which help to ensure that the co-design process is fair and equitable.

THE CO-DESIGNED PHASES WILL FOLLOW THE SCHEME SHOWN BELOW

Figure 2. Cos4Cloud approach to co-design (Cos4Cloud consortium 2023).

In conclusion, the use of a methodology for participatory co-design processes is essential in ensuring that the citizen science activity is transparent, participatory, and inclusive. By using a structured methodology, we can ensure that the co-design process is consistent, transparent, and accountable.

One of the objectives of this deliverable is to document/reflect the methodology that we are going to use when tackling tasks 2.2 (Participatory selection of new services for the eu-citizen.science platform) and 2.3 (Co-design and development of new services for the eu-citizen.science platform) in the ECS project.

Given that both tasks, by definition, require frameworks that allow the execution of participatory and co-design processes, it has been decided to elaborate an integral methodology that links both tasks and that allows to ensure a "start-to-finish" path: from the participatory processes for the selection of new services for the platform (T2.2) to the co-design, development and testing of these services (T2.3).

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, at least five new services will be developed throughout the co-design process in ECS. Thus, the ECS co-design process is planned as an iteration of annual cycles. Each cycle results in an updated version of the platform, in which one or more services chosen and co-designed with the community are implemented. One of the advantages of this kind of approach is that, if the methodology includes a co-evaluation phase, each cycle will be able to implement changes with respect to the previous ones based on the results of this co-evaluation, and also depending on the context of the project: what data is being obtained in the other work packages, what time and resources are available, etc.

2.2. Learning from Cos4Cloud: key concepts

As indicated in the GA, for the definition of the co-design process we will follow the Cos4Cloud co-design methodology (Guasch et al., 2022), extracting key concepts from it.

There are several key factors that make the Cos4Cloud guideline particularly useful in this project: it is designed (though not exclusively) for developing digital services; its approach is sufficiently accessible that any WP2 member can apply it, regardless of whether they have previous experience in participatory processes; and, above all, it focuses on the user experience during the process, rather than on tools. This makes it a process that has room for manoeuvre to adapt to emerging needs, which in a complex process with so many participants

are unpredictable. In fact, it is not intended to define a single path, but rather to describe a framework that allows decisions to be made to adapt to the context as necessary. To this end, there are several features:

In the Cos4Cloud guideline we can see how, for its digital services co-design process, three independent work teams are needed: the communication team, the co-design team, and the development team. This allows for a separation of responsibilities, with each team focusing on each of the main branches of the co-design process: Co-design, Development and Communication teams are identified in the co-design process in Cos4Cloud. In ECS we will also consider Co-evaluation as the other fundamental branch, as we will see later. Each of these teams plays a critical role in the success of the co-design methodology and is necessary for ensuring that the process is inclusive, effective, and well-documented.

The **communication team** is necessary to ensure that the co-design methodology is communicated effectively to all relevant stakeholders. This team is responsible for disseminating information about the co-design methodology, promoting stakeholder participation, and documenting the results of the process. Effective communication is crucial in ensuring that the co-design methodology is inclusive and that all stakeholders are aware of and able to participate in the process.

The **co-design team** is necessary to concretise the co-design activities to be carried out in each annual cycle, and supervise and moderate these co-design sessions. This team should be formed by people who are used to moderating and taking part in participatory processes, and is responsible for determining the goals and objectives of the co-design process, as well as the methods and techniques used to achieve them. The team helps to ensure that the co-design methodology is inclusive and considers the perspectives and needs of all stakeholders. In this sense, it could be said that the co-design team adopts two different perspectives depending on the stage of the process: a "facilitating" team perspective in the participative sessions (building dynamics so that decisions are taken collectively) and, on the other hand, an "executive" perspective in the rest of the process (initial selection of activities, setting deadlines, etc.).

The **development team** is necessary to ensure the technical implementation of the co-design methodology. This team is responsible for developing and testing the new services that are selected through the co-design process. The development team should work closely with the co-design and the communication team to ensure that the new services are in line with the goals and objectives of the co-design process, and their proper development.

In conclusion, the three working teams in the co-design methodology for the selection of new services for the ECS platform are all necessary for ensuring the inclusiveness, effectiveness, and documentation of the process. The communication team ensures effective communication and information dissemination, the co-design team ensures proper selection and execution of participatory sessions, and the development team ensures that the technical requirements of the selected services can be assured as well as their effective development.

This is the structure that the Cos4Cloud methodology uses to approach its co-design process. However, as we have already mentioned above we want to integrate a co-evaluation phase transversally to the rest of the co-design process. This would allow us to have a joint vision of the degree of satisfaction of the process itself, make adaptations to the methodology that increase the quality of the process, identify improvements that may arise in a "bottom-up" manner... In short, a perspective that seems to us to be more inclusive and that allows us, in some way, to "co-create" the methodology itself with the community. Thus, the co-design process in ECS needs to incorporate a fourth independent team: the co-evaluation team.

The **co-evaluation team** will be in charge of providing the necessary tools and managing the transversality of the co-evaluation phase. This will require the involvement of the other teams in order to identify all the activities and workshops to be carried out, define the KPIs needed to analyse their success, integrate the considerations of the co-evaluation team in the other phases, etc.

Last but not least, it is important that all the partners in the project understand and acknowledge the roles of the aforementioned teams, and it is advisable for the general coordination teams to have at least one person in close and constant contact with the communication, co-design, co-development and co-evaluation teams for quick validation and decision making. Such contact can be achieved by scheduling dedicated co-design meetings.

2.3. A yearly cycle in the ECS co-design process

As mentioned above, the ECS co-design process is composed of four annual cycles executed in an iterative way. Each of these cycles ensures participatory selection, co-design and development of an updated version of the ECS platform. An abstract view allows a Gantt chart of the different phases of a cycle:

GANTT CHART

Figure 3. Gantt chart of a yearly cycle in the ECS co-design process.

2.3.1. Phase 1 - Communication strategy

Responsible: Communication team

Subphases: 1.1 - Communication strategy (cross-cutting)

The main objective of applying a participatory co-design methodology is to build a strong community around the platform, in order to make the platform available to its users and transform it into an even more

useful tool. This objective cannot be achieved without an effective communication strategy that is implemented throughout the entire process, ensuring inclusive and representative participation of the community, full transparency in the co-design process, and accompanying both participants and stakeholders by providing the necessary information in a communication process that, due to the number of people involved, can be complex.

Furthermore, in ECS WP2, we believe that in a participatory process, the degree of satisfaction of the participants is as important as the results themselves. The participants of the sessions should feel listened to, that their contributions are valued, that they should have the opportunity to participate in future workshops, to know how their participation has contributed to the process and the results, and to know why some decisions are being taken and not others... In short, to transparently communicate with them.

Therefore, the communication strategy (**subphase 1.1** in the Gantt Chart) must be comprehensive and cover the entire process. To this end, the communication team must be coordinated and in constant exchange with the rest of the teams in the process, in order to ensure up-to-date information on the progress of the phases.

2.3.2. Phase 2 - Definition of the cycle: activities and timetable

Responsible: Co-design team

Subphases: 2.1 - Stakeholder mapping (coordinated with T2.1); 2.2 - Phase 3 definition; 2.3 - Conversion in User Stories; 2.4 - Analysis of the services to be developed; 2.5 - Phase 5 definition

As can be seen in the Gantt chart, this is an initial phase, and ensures the success of the participatory and co-design processes of phases 3 and 5. The co-design team is in charge of selecting the participatory activities that best fit the circumstances of each cycle regarding time, resources available, number of participants expected for that year (this information comes, inter alia, from **subphase 2.1.**), etc. It is at this phase, therefore, that it is important to manage expectations correctly. Each year will be subject to a different context. In the first year, for example, there will be less time available to carry out the cycle, so it will be in this phase that the timing and number of participatory events will have to be adjusted so that this mismatch does not affect the next cycles.

At the beginning of each cycle, and specifically at the start of the participatory phases (phases 3 and 5), the co-design team should select the participatory activities that best fit the context of the project (stakeholders involved, available resources, time management...) and consider the results of the co-evaluation phase so far.

The list of activities from which the co-design team has to make its selection is varied, allowing for a large number of combinations that can best fit the context of each cycle (depending on the number of participants, the difference between their profiles, degree of experience, etc.). Most of the activities come from "Co-Design as a service: Methodological guide" (Guasch et al. 2022). A practical guide developed to implement the co-design methodology applied in Cos4Cloud (which can be found described in detail in Annex B). Other activities (adjusted to the specific needs of our project) have been described by the ECS team and can be found in Annex A.

In this phase, two important milestones can be considered: **subphase 2.2**, which results in the beginning of phase 3; and **subphase 2.5**, which results in the beginning of phase 5. Thus, the selection of activities will attend to slightly different criteria in each phase. While for phase 3 it will be important to consider the number and the profile of potential participants, in phase 5 the results of phase 3 will be key: what kind of services have been selected, what level of depth can be reached in co-design sessions, etc. Therefore, effective communication between the co-design team and the development team will be essential in this phase.

Table 7. Table of activities that can be carried out in a cycle.

Selection of recommended activities		
Phase	Activity	Objective
1, 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder mapping 	reaching out to more participants, identifying communities we do not reach, stakeholder groups, ensures inclusiveness
3, 6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Needs identification workshop Brainstorming Specific survey/s 	identification of new services for the platform, conformity with the current platform status, suggested modifications to existing services
5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mindmapping Parallel boards Wheels 	design and prototyping of the service
5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Usability testing Usability report Value opportunity analysis 	identification of errors, feedback from the community, evaluation of the degree of satisfaction with the development and achievement of the objectives
3, 5, 6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specific survey Triangular groups 	co-evaluation of the methodology itself. Input of feedback in order to make the necessary modifications to improve.

2.3.3. Phase 3 - Activities for participatory selection

Responsible: Co-design team

Subphases: 3.1 - Participatory selection activities

The main objective of phase 3 is to select the services that will be developed, co-designed and tested in phases 4 and 5. The differences based on the context of each cycle can be considerable. In some cycles, an online survey conducted to strategic profiles may be sufficient. In other cycles, face-to-face workshops may be considered to carry out brainstorming, moderated debates, etc. Therefore, it is difficult to predict how the activities carried out in this phase will evolve over the years. However, the main objective of phase 2 is to have transformed this context into a suitable environment for the selected participatory activities. What is important to us is to be transparent with the participants about the reasons that motivate each cycle to adopt its own modifications.

The co-design team will be in charge of moderating the participatory session/s (**subphase 3.1**) of this phase. Once finalised, the co-design team together with the development team will convert the results of the participatory sessions into a "User Story" format (**subphase 2.3**). This format provides a structure for articulating how a user will interact with the platform and what their expected outcomes are. By focusing on the user's perspective, the "User Story" format ensures that the design and development of the platform are aligned with the needs and desires of its intended users.

The "User Story" format can also help facilitate communication between stakeholders and the development team, leading to more effective collaboration and better decision making (Höst et al., 2011). It also allows stakeholders to communicate their needs and requirements in a way that is easily digestible and understandable to the development team. This helps to reduce misunderstandings and improve the overall design process.

Once the results of the participatory sessions are available in a User Story format, they will be analysed in order to establish the final selection of services to be developed on the platform. This selection (**subphase 2.4**) will be based on the results obtained through the participatory processes, but also taking into account the technological criteria of the development team, whose responsibility will be to ensure that the selected services can be developed satisfactorily. In this way, the co-design team will ensure that in the conversion process to User Stories, the wishes of the community are faithfully respected. In addition, it will ensure that the selected services are aligned with the project's objectives, as well as with the principles of citizen science, open science and FAIR. On the other hand, the development team will bring a more pragmatic view, ensuring that the selected services can be successfully developed within the deadlines. Once again, the most important aspect of this methodology is to effectively analyse and communicate the results of this selection to the participants: explain why some services have not been selected, if it would be possible to develop them in the next cycles, carry out a co-evaluation of the selection process, etc.

2.3.4. Phase 4 - Development of selected services

Responsible: Development team

Subphases: 4.1 - First stage of development; 4.2 - Final stage of development.

The development team is responsible for managing this phase, during which the services selected by the community will be developed. It is essential, therefore, that the service selection has been realistic with the available time to develop them, in order to meet the deadlines for launching the updated platform (planned due dates are July 2023, July 2024, July 2025 and July 2026). In addition, the correct management of this phase takes into account the co-design and testing activities that will be carried out in phase 5. We could practically say that both phases, 4 and 5, are dependent on each other, with phase 5 being the one in which the participatory processes of development (testing/co-design) take place and phase 4 being exclusively the responsibility of the development team. In this way, at the beginning of this phase (**subphase 4.1**), the development team will draw up a timetable to guarantee the correct development of the selected services: dates for the first betas, topics to be addressed in the testing/co-design sessions, deadlines for results, etc. Once again, it will be essential that the communication team is aware of all these decisions in order to inform the participants.

Once the participatory sessions have been completed (both co-design and testing, where appropriate), the final stage of service development will take place (**subphase 4.2**), allowing the platform to be updated.

2.3.5. Phase 5 - Co-design and testing

Responsible: Co-design team

Subphases: 5.1 - Co-design activities; 5.2 - Testing activities

This phase includes all participatory activities related to the co-design, prototyping and testing of the services to be developed in each cycle. As previously explained, the selection of participatory activities to be carried out in this phase will be established based on community suggestions (phases 2 and 3) and the technical criteria of the development team (phase 4). The co-design team will be responsible for moderating the

participatory sessions, ensuring equitable, inclusive participation where all participants feel heard. However, the development team will be responsible for ensuring that the sessions conducted generate useful results for the objectives of this phase.

In this sense, we can distinguish two types of sessions: the co-design/prototyping sessions (**sub-phase 5.1**), where the main functionalities and characteristics of the services to be developed are decided; and the testing sessions (**sub-phase 5.2**), where bug tracking and the last stage of feedback are carried out, leading to the final development of the services by the Development team.

2.3.6. Phase 6 - Co-evaluation

Responsible: Co-evaluation team

Subphases: 6.1 - Co-evaluation activities (cross-cutting); 6.2 - Co-evaluation results

This phase is transversal throughout the entire process (**subphase 6.1**), however we have placed it at the end because it generates the final output of each cycle (**subphase 6.2**). Its results allow us to have a comprehensive view of the state of the co-design process, and make real-time modifications to improve participation, strengthen the existing community, and generally achieve better results.

The importance of co-evaluation within participatory processes has gained increasing recognition as it offers communities the opportunity to participate in the whole evaluation process, express their views and effectively influence decision-making. Studies show that co-evaluation can enhance the rigour, credibility and legitimacy of the participatory process, resulting in the creation of interventions that are more aligned with the needs of the communities involved (Brown & Knight, 2015).

For the success of the co-evaluation phase, it is important to develop a comprehensive plan in conjunction with the rest of the teams and partners involved in the process, adapting it to the configuration adopted by the other phases.

2.4. Timetable approach for an annual cycle in the ECS co-design process

It is important to understand that, in participatory processes where different profiles with different understandings and degrees of experience on the issues to be discussed coincide, it is necessary to be open to admitting modifications in real time that facilitate obtaining useful results. It is therefore difficult to define a single roadmap that fits all cycles. However, a first approximation could be the one shown in the following table (Table 8):

Table 8. Timetable approach for an annual cycle in the ECS co-design process.

Subphase	Activity	Team responsible	Support teams	Objective	Outputs
1.1	Communication plan	Communication team	Co-design team, Development team	To design a communication plan adapted to each year, which is essential for the achievement of the project's objectives. It should cover each phase of the co-design cycle.	Communication strategy
2.1	- Stakeholder mapping	Co-design team	Communication team	Reaching out to more participants, identifying communities we do not reach, stakeholder groups, ensures inclusiveness	Target groups
2.2	Phase 3 definition	Co-design team	Co-evaluation team, Communication team, Development team	Define the activities for that cycle, according to the time and resources available.	Timetable for phase 3
3.1	Participatory selection activities - Brainstorming - Specific survey/s - Mindmapping - Parallel boards	Co-design team	Communication team, Development team	Identification of new services for the platform, conformity with the current status, suggested modifications to existing services	Activity outputs
2.3	Conversion in User Stories	Co-design team	Development team	Conversion of activity outputs to user stories	Identification of new services
2.4	Analysis of the services to be developed	Development team	Communication team	Evaluation of the services proposed by the community, and elaboration of a report about what will be developed and what will not, and why.	Identification of services to be developed

2.5	Phase 5 definition	Co-design team	Co-evaluation team, Communication team, Development team	Is the environment favourable for co-design activities in the design and prototyping stages?	Timetable for phase 5
4.1	First stage of development	Development team		Development of new services	Beta services
5.1	Co-design activities - <i>Mindmapping</i> - <i>Parallel boards</i>	Co-design team	Communication team, Development team	Co-design and prototyping of the service	Services co-design
5.2	Testing activities - <i>Usability testing</i> - <i>Usability report</i>	Co-design team, Development team	Communication team, Development team	Bug tracking, feedback from the community, evaluation of the degree of satisfaction with the development and achievement of the objectives	Bug and error logs
4.2	Final stage of development	Development team		Final service development	Final service/s
6.1	Transversal co-evaluation activities - <i>Specific survey</i> - <i>Triangular groups</i>	Co-evaluation team	Co-design team, Communication team, Development team	Co-evaluation of the methodology itself. Input of feedback in order to make the necessary modifications to improve the methodology.	Feedback on the methodology
6.2	Co-evaluation results	Co-evaluation team	Co-design team, Communication team, Development team	Analysis of the results of the co-evaluation: what worked and what didn't, and how can we fix it	Summary report of the results of the co-evaluation of that cycle and recommendations for the next cycle

3. Inclusivity

3.1. ECS approach towards inclusiveness

Citizen science has emerged as a means to democratise science by involving diverse individuals in various stages of the research process, as pointed out by Hecker et al. (2018). This approach offers an opportunity to rethink how inclusiveness is factored into knowledge production by raising questions such as who participates in science, what constitutes participation, what kind of knowledge is considered scientific, and who determines the research questions, as highlighted by Vohland et al. (2021).

However, since citizen science is a social activity, it is influenced by factors such as ethnicity, income, age, context, and cultural practices. From recent debates and given that participants in any kind of scientific endeavour are overwhelmingly white adults, above median income, with a college degree, citizen science as a field has been questioned, and it is true that it is not a purely egalitarian field, open and available to all members of our societies, particularly those underrepresented in science. From this point, some question whether the term “citizen” is a barrier in itself to inclusion, rebranding projects as “community science”. As argued in Cooper et al. (2021), swapping terms are not a benign action by itself, and citizen science projects will only become inclusive through action. The challenge of inclusion in citizen science reveals that intentions or words are not enough, and that inclusive citizen science should be expanded so that no community groups in our societies remain underrepresented.

With a specific focus and WP on equity and inclusivity, the ECS project can introduce new and diverse groups to scientific participation, which will result in novel perspectives and benefits. To achieve inclusivity, ECS will consider factors such as language used, cultural differences in territories, accessibility, and socioeconomic status when designing and implementing activities. This can involve using plain language that everybody understands, providing translators or interpreters, creating accessible materials, and ensuring that the project is affordable and available for whoever wishes to participate. To sum up, ECS strives to be inclusive, flexible, and adaptable to ensure that traditionally underrepresented citizens in science can participate in the research process.

3.2. What will we do?

ECS aims at positioning Europe as a global leader in citizen science, therefore, it is paramount to make citizen science “[to look more like our societies](#)” (Mervis 2018). For this, the consortium commits to bring inclusiveness by clearing away barriers in all ECS activities through giving traditional underrepresented groups the opportunity to participate in the project at any stage or level. **ECS will apply a flexible approach**, as depicted in figure 4, the project was designed with the understanding that participants may have different levels of expertise and availability. For example, some participants may be able to commit more time to the project than others, or they may have different technological capabilities. Where possible, ECS will allow and recognise both active participants and those who will drop in and out or pick small contributions, allowing each citizen to participate in the way their availability and interest allows.

Figure 4. DITOs escalator framework for public engagement (Skarlatidou & Haklay 2021).

The ECS inclusiveness approach is going to be developed as a cross-cutting aspect throughout the whole project, and will be implemented around four main elements:

- Geographical spread of citizen science
- Gender balance
- Inclusion of traditionally underrepresented groups in citizen science
- Ad hoc inclusive strategies

Approaches and actions throughout the ECS project duration:

- ECS will provide clear guidance and support to ensure that participants can contribute meaningfully, regardless of their individual background and circumstances.
- ECS will adapt to changing circumstances, such as unexpected events or other disruptions that may impact any stage of the project. The Consortium commits to adjusting timelines, methods, or locations as necessary to ensure that the project can engage traditionally underrepresented groups of citizens.
- To ensure inclusivity in events, workshops, seminars, and other ECS activities, co-creation with diverse perspectives is crucial. This process needs to be implemented during the activity's design phase, rather than as an afterthought.
- While there is no universal manual or protocol on inclusivity, the extent of inclusion will depend on the context, specific activities, budget and human resources. This means that ECS will integrate as many perspectives as possible from backgrounds at every stage of the project considering the above restrictions. By co-creating/co-designing activities during the design phase and integrating an inclusive perspective, activities can be more accessible, equitable, and effective. This approach promotes meaningful engagement and contributes to a more diverse and inclusive citizen science community.

- Broadly speaking, frame dependence⁴ refers to the notion that human beings tend to respond to situations based on how those situations are presented and framed. This can have significant implications for the implementation of ECS activities, as it highlights the importance of considering the context in which activities are carried out. In the context of ECS, understanding is frame dependent, meaning that the way in which ECS Ambassadors, Affiliated Entities and partners will frame the different activities can influence how participants engage with ECS. For instance, the way in which an ECS activity is described or the language used to communicate can affect whether or not certain citizen groups feel attracted or not. One critical factor to consider when framing citizen science activities is culture.
- Culture plays a significant role in shaping how citizens perceive and respond to messages. At this point, ECS Ambassadors and the Affiliated Entities will play a crucial role since they represent different organisations, expertise profiles and territories that can incorporate cultural considerations into the design of ECS activities.
- At the European level, in 2018, ECSA in cooperation with the Living Knowledge Network for science shops and community-based research, set up the [working group on Empowerment, Inclusiveness and Equity](#) – which is currently one of the most active and knowledge-based spaces for these issues – to establish different collaborations and knowledge sharing. The aim is that more people from diverse backgrounds can actively participate in citizen science activities with collaborative approaches to generate societal impact addressing their needs. Some ECS partners are already actively collaborating in this working group, and will further advocate for greater knowledge sharing.
- Appreciating and explicitly acknowledging the importance of a citizen's contribution is one of the *Ten Principles of Citizen Science* elaborated by ECSA (ECSA 2015). ECS will acknowledge the importance of participant's individual and collective contributions by providing regular feedback, giving them the opportunity to take more responsibility if wished so, inviting them to participate in seminars, symposiums and conferences, and acknowledging them in scientific publications.
- ECS adheres to [Principle Two: Leave No One Behind \(LNOB\) of the United Nations](#) (UN), which is the central promise of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and its Sustainable Development Goals. It posits the commitment of all UN Member States to eradicate poverty in all its forms, end discrimination and exclusion, as well as reduce inequalities and vulnerabilities – also in science – that leave people behind.

4. Evaluation and co-evaluation of community engagement and co-design activities

Co-evaluation is an essential component of citizen social science projects that involve a wide range of different profiles such as in the case of the co-design process in ECS. It enables different teams to gain deep insights into the effectiveness and transformative power of the process, leading to more valuable outcomes and impacts for

⁴ For further information see TEDx Talks (2017) in the references.

all stakeholders involved. To ensure the success of co-evaluation in a co-design process, several good practices should be considered. The following ideas on co-evaluation are based on the whitepaper by Kieslinger et al. (2022).

First, co-evaluation should be an integral part of the project from the very beginning, co-designed into the action(s) and not seen as an “add-on” or external to specific citizen science activities. This ensures that evaluation is integrated into the process design and is aligned with the goals of all stakeholders involved. Adaptive project management is also critical to support co-evaluation, as it may require pivoting and adapting during the research process.

Also, it is recommended that there be a team dedicated exclusively to co-evaluation – depending on the size of the activities and on the project. In the case of the co-design of services for the platform within ECS, the co-evaluation team will consist of a couple of project colleagues also involved in this participatory process as part of the co-design team. This team should have the necessary expertise and experience to manage the evaluation process effectively, and to facilitate the involvement of all stakeholders in the evaluation process. Co-actors involved in the process should also be sensitised to the concept of co-evaluation and should have the opportunity and space to build capacity on co-evaluation.

Moreover, co-evaluation should focus on actionable results and contribute actively to transformation and change. To achieve this, all the teams should develop clear and measurable objectives that align with the goals of all stakeholders involved. The use of flexible KPIs that need to be co-created and negotiated in a participatory way is recommended, as it ensures that all stakeholders have input into the evaluation process and ensures the evaluation is aligned with the goals of all stakeholders involved.

The recommendations on co-evaluation presented in the whitepaper are formulated having in mind citizen science projects with a transformative aim. This is not the case for the co-evaluation of the co-design activities within ECS to develop new services and features for the eu-citizen.science platform. Therefore, an adaptation and interpretation of the principles will be done to better fit the co-design process in ECS. A simplified example of how co-evaluation could take place within the co-design of ECS could be to 1) share post-co-design activity surveys with all participants, 2) then analyse the data within the ECS team co-evaluation team and 3) organise triangular groups (see Annex A) with three or four participants (external to the project) after the end of each co-design cycle to jointly reflect about the co-design process and distil lessons learned and potential improvements for the next co-design cycle. In short, the co-evaluation phase is conceived as an active listening process, in which participants take the floor and reflect on how the co-design process in ECS could be improved.

In addition, inclusivity and responsiveness are essential principles of co-evaluation. It is important to ensure that all stakeholders have equal opportunities to participate in the evaluation process, regardless of their background or level of expertise. This corresponds with the approach to inclusiveness in ECS presented in section 3. Co-evaluation should also be responsive to the needs and interests of all stakeholders involved, including the wider community. Therefore, responsible process management is a key challenge of co-evaluation, including the facilitation of robust inclusive facilitation and community building. Co-evaluation often relies on face-to-face interactions, which may pose a barrier to participation for some participants, while it benefits others. Therefore, the co-evaluation team should consider alternative methods of engagement, such as online tools and virtual meetings, to ensure that all stakeholders can participate in the evaluation process.

In conclusion, the co-evaluation phase within a complex process such as the co-design process in ECS is critical to achieving valuable outcomes and impacts for all stakeholders involved. By implementing the good practices outlined above, project teams can ensure that co-evaluation is integrated into the project design, that it focuses

on actionable results, is flexible and inclusive, and is managed responsibly. Co-evaluation can be costly in terms of time and resources, but it provides deep insights into the effectiveness and transformative power of participatory activities. As such, it is a valuable tool for learning from citizen science and contributing to social transformation and change.

The *co-evaluation* mentioned as part of the co-design activities should not be confused with the *evaluation* of community engagement events mentioned in section 1.3.3. The evaluation of the community engagement events will be an internal activity solely carried out by members of the ECS consortium based on the information from registration forms, post-event surveys and the team's reflections on the events organised. While they can be complementary and lessons learned drawn from each exercise can be helpful for the other, they are thought of as separate tasks.

5. Concluding remarks and next steps

This document presents the plan for the community engagement events in T2.1 and the co-design methodologies to be followed in T2.2 and T2.3 of ECS. It also provides insights into ECS's approach towards inclusiveness and suggests actions that the consortium can take to support inclusiveness in project activities. This report aims to serve as a guide or reference document to plan the activities mentioned throughout the project. As the first rounds of community engagement events and co-design activities are carried out over the next months, the plan will be adapted and further refined as needed. However, beyond the activities of T2.1, T2.2 and T2.3, this deliverable can be useful to standardise how we go about organising events in ECS and how to include inclusion aspects and considerations.

The next first steps are to continue the stakeholder mapping and the identification of interesting events to run community engagement events (both as an iterative process that will continue throughout the project) and to start planning the first activities in the different phases of the co-design process.

References

- Bonney, R., Cooper, C. B., Dickinson, J., Kelling, S., Phillips, T., Rosenberg, K. V., & Shirk, J. (2009). Citizen Science: A Developing Tool for Expanding Science Knowledge and Scientific Literacy, *BioScience*, 59(11), 977–984, <https://doi.org/10.1525/bio.2009.59.11.9>
- Brown, L., & Knight, P. (2015). The role of co-evaluation in participatory research: An exploratory study. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 18(5), 471-487. doi: 10.1080/13645579.2013.806441
- Cambridge University Press (2023). Outreach. In *Cambridge Dictionary*. <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/outreach>
- Campisi, D., Nyffeler, N., Roulet Schwab, D., Le Fort, V. & Bergeron, L. (2018, September 25). The benefits and challenges of co-creation with seniors: an interdisciplinary social innovation project designed to improve quality of life. Open Living Lab Days 2018 (OLLD18), Geneva, Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1434992>
- Cooper, C., Hawn, C., Larson, L., Parrich, J., Bowser, G., Cavalier, D., Dunn, R., Hacklay, M., Gupta, K., Osborne, N., Johnson, V., Katti, M., Leggett, Z., Wilson, O., Wilson, S. (2021). Inclusion in citizen science: The conundrum of rebranding. *Science*, Vol 372, Issue 6549. <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.abi6487>
- Cohn, M.: User stories applied for agile software development. In: Cohn, M. (ed.) 13th ed. Pearson Education Inc., Indiana (2009).
- Cos4Cloud consortium (2023). Cos4Cloud website: Co-design & testing. Available at: <https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/the-project/this-is-cos4cloud/co-design-methodology/>
- ECSA (European Citizen Science Association). 2015. Ten Principles of Citizen Science. Berlin. <http://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/XPR2N>
- EU-Citizen.Science Consortium (2019). EU-Citizen.Science: D2.1: Stakeholders, Network & Community Mapping Report, ECSA, Berlin. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3465726>
- European Commission (2016). Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020 v3.1. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf
- European Research Executive Agency (2023). Horizon Europe Widening - Who should apply. Available at: https://rea.ec.europa.eu/horizon-europe-widening-who-should-apply_en
- Guasch, Blanca, Amo, Alex, Hernández, Miguel, Arias, Rosa, Liñán, Sonia, Piera, Jaume, Justamante, Ángela, Fabó, Claudia, & Soacha, Karen. (2022). Co-design as a service: Methodological guide. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472450>
- Hecker, S., Hacklay, M., Bowser, A., Makuch, Z., Vogel, J., & Bonn, A. (2018). Citizen science: Innovation in open science, society and policy. London UCL Press.

Höst, M., Conboy, K., Finlay, J., Robertson, T., Greenberg, S., & Pauker, S. (2015). User stories: A method for stakeholder engagement and requirements capture in healthcare innovation. In Proceedings of the 33rd annual ACM conference on human factors in computing systems (pp. 879-888). ACM.

INCENTIVE Consortium (2022). D2.3 Manual for Citizen Science community building. INCENTIVE project. Retrieved from: https://incentive-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/INCENTIVE-D2.3_Manual-for-Citizen-Science-Community-Building-final.pdf

Kasperowski, D., Kullenberg, C., & Mäkitalo, Å. (2017, February 27). Embedding Citizen Science in Research: Forms of engagement, scientific output and values for science, policy and society. <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/tfsg>

Kieslinger, Barbara, Mayer, Katja, Schaefer, Teresa, & Schuerz, Stefanie. (2022). Whitepaper on Co-evaluation of Citizen Social Science. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7117123>

Mervis, Jeffrey (2018). Citizen science needs to look more like society, report says. *Science* 2018, aav9305. doi:10.1126/science.aav9305

National Coordination Center for Public Engagement. (n.d.). "What is public engagement?". Retrieved from What is public engagement? NCCPE, accessed on 17.02.2023. Available at: <https://www.publicengagement.ac.uk/about-engagement/what-public-engagement>

Ospina-Pinillos L, Davenport T, Mendoza Diaz A, Navarro-Mancilla A, Scott E, Hickie I (2019). Using Participatory Design Methodologies to Co-Design and Culturally Adapt the Spanish Version of the Mental Health eClinic: Qualitative Study *J Med Internet Res* 2019; 21 (8):e14127 DOI: 10.2196/14127

Rüfenacht, S. *et al.* (2021). Communication and Dissemination in Citizen Science. In: , *et al.* The Science of Citizen Science. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_24

Sanders, Elizabeth & Stappers, Pieter Jan. (2008). Co-creation and the New Landscapes of Design. *CoDesign*. 4. 5-18. 10.1080/15710880701875068.

Senabre Hidalgo, E., Perelló, J., Becker, F., Bonhoure, I., Legris, M., Cigarini, A. (2021). Participation and Co-creation in Citizen Science. In: , *et al.* The Science of Citizen Science. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_11

Skarlatidou, Artemis & Haklay, Muki. (2021). Citizen science impact pathways for a positive contribution to public participation in science. *Journal of Science Communication*. 20. A02. 10.22323/2.20060202.

TEDx Talks [TEDxTalks]. (2017, June). *How words change minds: The science of storytelling* | Nat Kendall-Taylor | TEDxMidAtlanticSalon. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y8wol2nGSpY>

Veeckman, C., Talboom, S., Gijssels, L., Devoghel, H., Duerinckx, A. (2019). Communication in Citizen Science. A practical guide to communication and engagement in citizen science. SCIVIL, Leuven, Belgium. Available here: <https://www.scivil.be/en/book/communication-citizen-science>

Vohland, K., Land-Zandstra, A., Ceccaroni, L., Lemmens, R., Perelló, J., Ponti, M., Samson, R., Wagenknecht, K. (2021). "The Science of Citizen Science", Springer. 1-520.

Annex A – Description of additional activities for the ECS co-design process

Activity

Triangular groups

Phase	Time frame	Group size	Group profile
5, 6	70-120 min	3 people + moderator	Users, participants

Description

The triangular group is a qualitative analysis technique that fluctuates between interviews and focus groups. It consists of three participants and a moderator; the small number of participants places the triangular group at the limit of the group situation. It requires the collection of individual experiences, personal feelings, the individuality of the project participant, but is not limited to a single experience, but also involves group experience, collective reflection, comparison of common experiences or differentiation between the participants.

It is particularly useful for the reflection on a jointly lived participatory process or for the evaluation of a tool, as it forces the participants to go beyond personal experience and to reflect together, but does not fall into anonymous groupness. Moreover, several of them can be carried out, as it is relatively easy to bring three people together.

Work map

Activity

Needs identification workshop

Phase	Time frame	Group size	Group profile
3	90 min	+10 people	Users, experts

Description

The identification workshop aims to trace the different problems of the community, make them visible and establish relationships between them or prioritise them. It focuses on the problems of the participants, seeking to identify the main needs of the group.

To do this, each person is asked to situate each of the problems they experience in relation to the researched environment in a common space, visible to all participants. In a second step, the common causes of these problems are identified through the group and a list of needs is made, knowing to what extent each of them is shared by the different participants.

This workshop can easily be complemented in the same or a following session with a Mind mapping or a brainstorming of solutions. The latter, for example, consists of dividing into groups of three, each group having to come up with a solution to each identified need. This can be completed with a matrix of how many needs each solution covers. Finally, there is a selection or prioritisation of those that the group considers most important.

Work map

<u>PROBLEM</u>	DROUGHT	PLAGUES	WEEDS	LACK IRRIGATION
DROUGHT	X	DROUGHT	DROUGHT	DROUGHT
PLAGUES	X	X	PLAGUES	LACK IRRIGATION
WEEDS	X	X	X	LACK IRRIGATION
LACK IRRIGATION	X	X	X	X

Annex B – Activities extracted from Guasch et al. (2022)

Activity

Stakeholder Mapping

Phase	Time frame	Group size	Group profile
1	20-40 min	6-12 people	Service staff

Description

Stakeholder maps are a useful resource to identify and consolidate in a visual way all the people/institutions involved in a project. These maps are built at the start of a project to determine who is going to be engaged in the different phases, and in what way: who will be responsible, accountable, consulted, informed, etc.

Stakeholder maps are usually created in a speculative way, as a brainstorming, and it is important that it be done exhaustively, including all the people who are or can be of interest for the project. In more advanced stages of the project, this map can and should be updated, generating a real map of who has been involved in the project at the end.

There are different ways of structuring the stakeholders: by sector, field, interest, expertise, level of involvement, etc. All of them are valid, and we will apply the one that is most useful for us each time.

Work map

Guasch, B. et al. (2022). Co-design as a service: Methodological guide. Cos4Cloud. Zenodo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472450>

Activity

Brainstorming graphic organiser

Phase	Time frame	Group size	Group profile
2	20-40 min	6-12 people	Service staff, Citizens

Description

Brainstorming is a widely used method to generate new concepts in relation to a specific challenge or topic. It is about generating the largest number of ideas, accepting everything that comes out, without judgement or criticism.

Brainstorming creates a safe forum of free expression and association of ideas, which promotes creativity. This is why this technique is very useful whenever we need to have quantity over quality of ideas – and usually, when there is quantity, quality arises.

Brainstorming graphic organisers are structures that help generate new knowledge with the freedom of brainstorming, while following a specific visualisation framework, such as:

1. Concept webs, to develop a central question or topic.
2. Tree diagrams, to define hierarchy or a classification system.
3. Flow diagrams, to show a process or cause and effect of interrelated elements within a system.

Work map

Guasch, B. et al. (2022). Co-design as a service: Methodological guide. Cos4Cloud. Zenodo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472450>

Activity

Mind mapping

Phase	Time frame	Group size	Group profile
2	20-40 min	6-12 people	Technological service staff

Description

Mind maps are a very useful tool to capture in a simple scheme the ramification of concepts from a central concept.

The way people think is rarely linear. Our brains make neural connections in the form of networks, and the problems and challenges we face in our daily lives are interconnected with all parts of our reality in the same way.

Mind maps help capture these networks. It is a tool for visualising thought in a diagrammatic way, and is characterised by being a powerful mnemonic resource that promotes the understanding of a problem space.

To create a mind map, we just need to identify a core issue to work on, start drawing outward extensions and label them with simple verb-noun pairs or noun clusters. Once the primary connections are identified, we should continue making secondary connections and free associations, to expand the map more and more.

Work map

Guasch, B. et al. (2022). Co-design as a service: Methodological guide. Cos4Cloud. Zenodo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472450>

Activity

Parallel boards

Phase	Time frame	Group size	Group profile
3	120-140 min	6-12 people	Technological service staff, experts, users

Description

The “parallel boards” methodology arises from two very simple methodologies, from outside the realm of co-design. These are the interviews (from journalism) and the Q&A (Questions and Answers) format that is often used in conferences and forums. Both are based on a question and answer system, and this is how this collaborative methodology has been designed.

The fact that it is called “parallel boards” is because in the work map there are two boards that look identical but are not. One of them is intended for an expert audience, while the other is addressed to an inexperienced audience, and the questions asked in each one are different.

At the end of the dynamic, two general questions are asked to both groups of participants to conclude the session.

Work map

Step by step

1. Place yourselves on the upper part of the work map. Here you can find an infographic describing the service being developed. The software developer should explain how it works and at what stage of development it is.
2. Divide the participants into two groups. Experts (other software developers or technical profiles) should be in one of them, while non-experts (end users) should be in the other one.

3. One by one, go asking and answering the questions that are displayed on the map. These questions will be specific for each service and the software developer should be the one who writes them. Here is an example of questions for a specific service for environmental citizen observatories:
 - a. Users: *How and for what do you use this service? What functionalities should it have? How should the service relate to the observatories that you use? How do you picture the user interface of the service or how would you like it to be? What environmental data might be relevant to include in the service and how could we classify them?*
 - b. Experts: *What is your platform about and how does it work? What data does your observatory manage and how do you collect it? How do you process and validate those data afterwards? What environmental data might be relevant to include in the service and how could we classify them?*
 4. Once both groups have answered all the questions, you can move into a common group to answer the concluding questions. If the two groups go at different paces and one of them needs more time than the other, you can also address these questions separately and then mix the answers afterwards. Here is an example of questions for the same service:
 - a. Concluding questions: *What interesting interactions or added value can the service contribute to the observatories? What interesting interactions or added value can the observatories contribute to the service?*
 - b. These concluding questions should spark some debate among participants. Set aside some time to let people discuss this point.
 - c. Once the debate is over, you can conclude the session.
 5. And... congratulations! You have finished the session and now you have new inputs for the service. Hooray!
-

Guasch, B. et al. (2022). Co-design as a service: Methodological guide. Cos4Cloud. Zenodo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472450>

Activity

Wheels

Phase	Time frame	Group size	Group profile
3, 5	120-140 min	6-12 people	Technological service staff, experts, users

Description

The “wheels” methodology is based, on the one hand, on the SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats), which seeks to reveal the strong and weak points of a service, both internal and external.

On the other hand, this methodology is also based on desirability testing, which analyses whether a service – or a part of it – is liked or disliked by users, and how they would change or adapt it.

Work map

Step by step

1. Place yourselves on the upper wheel.
2. Starting at the top and going clockwise, go answering all the questions that are written on the wheel. These are:
 - a. How would you use this service?
 - b. What are the most interesting features? (strengths)
 - c. Would you change anything? (weaknesses and opportunities)
 - d. Is there anything missing? (weaknesses and opportunities)

- e. How can this service contribute to [the main goal of the service; e.g. the quantity and quality of data in Citizen Science Observatories]?
 - f. What could go wrong? (threats)
 3. At any moment during the dynamic, you can group similar ideas, categorise them, or organise them in any way in which they make more sense to you.
 4. Once you are done, situate yourself on the lower wheel.
 5. In the order you prefer, go filling in ideas about how you would like the service to be in relation to the four aspects shown. These are:
 - a. Functionality
 - b. Interface
 - c. Architecture
 - d. [The specific topic your service is addressing; e.g. Citizen Science]
 6. Once you have filled all the areas with your thoughts, you can group the comments that are similar, categorise ideas or organise them as you prefer.
 7. And... congratulations! You have finished the session and now you have new inputs for the service. Hooray!
-

Guasch, B. et al. (2022). Co-design as a service: Methodological guide. Cos4Cloud. Zenodo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472450>

Activity

Usability testing

Phase	Time frame	Group size	Group profile
5	60-240 min	2-4 people	Users, experts

Description

Usability testing is an evaluation method that focuses on people and their tasks, and allows software developers to observe the individual experiences of different people, and how they execute certain processes in their services.

The tests are organised and designed around specific user stories or scenarios, which represent real cases encountered by the end users of the services.

This methodology usually follows the format of the think-aloud technique, in which the users have to say everything they are doing out loud while executing it. This allows us to see if the user is understanding the task, if they are taking the appropriate steps to complete it, if they express surprise or some other emotion, if they make a mistake, if they have to go back a step in the process, etc., as well as reveal problems or unclear steps.

Work map

	TASK DESCRIPTION	USER'S COMMENTS	EVALUATOR'S COMMENTS
STEP 1	~~~~~ ~~~~~	~~~~~ ~~~~~	~~~~~ ~~~~~
STEP 2	~~~~~ ~~~~~	~~~~~ ~~~~~	~~~~~ ~~~~~
STEP 3	~~~~~ ~~~~~	~~~~~ ~~~~~	~~~~~ ~~~~~
STEP 4	~~~~~ ~~~~~	~~~~~ ~~~~~	~~~~~ ~~~~~

Guasch, B. et al. (2022). Co-design as a service: Methodological guide. Cos4Cloud. Zenodo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472450>

Activity

Usability reporting

Phase	Time frame	Group size	Group profile
5	60-240 min	2-4 people	Users, experts

Description

Usability reports are a resource or technique that allows to clearly highlight which parts of the user interface should be improved, modified or fixed.

A few years ago, all usability reports were done in the format of long documents. Today, these reports can take different formats, including video and audio. The relevance of the report is not so much its final format, but rather the user input found in it.

In a collaborative activity where you want participants to build a usability report, the work groups should be small and have very clear objectives, as well as a structure to follow with the following sections: executive summary, total number of issues found, list of problems that should be fixed, reports on positive things, detailed task and scenario descriptions.

The time required for this methodology is highly variable depending on the complexity of the service to be evaluated.

Work map

Guasch, B. et al. (2022). Co-design as a service: Methodological guide. Cos4Cloud. Zenodo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472450>

Activity

Value opportunity analysis

Phase	Time frame	Group size	Group profile
5	60-240 min	6-12 people	Users, experts

Description

Value opportunity analyses are an assessment of a service’s aspirational attributes. They collect the intangible qualities that the user perceives out of it.

Thus, this analysis goes beyond the execution of tasks and the user interface, to focus on the emotions and sensations that a service transmits. Some of the fields to evaluate are: emotion, aesthetics, identity, impact, ergonomics, quality, etc.

It is, therefore, a very subjective analysis, and the evaluations of each individual will be biased by their culture and identity. This is why a value opportunity analysis usually results in different ratings of each of the fields, and often generates discussions among the development team members.

However, it is critical to understand this more subjective part of the users, since it will determine why they choose your service over others, or vice versa.

Work map

Guasch, B. et al. (2022). Co-design as a service: Methodological guide. Cos4Cloud. Zenodo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472450>